

HISTOPATHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN OSTEOARTHRITIS INDUCED WISTAR RATS ON TREATMENT WITH *CISSUS QUADRANGULARIS* AND *ZINGIBER OFFICINALE*

Chakrapani Cheekavolu¹, Pradeep T², Nalinidevi Jayabalan^{3*}, J Viswanath⁴,

S Sankaraiah⁵

¹Department of Pharmacology, Karpagam Faculty of Medical Science and Research,
Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India , 641032.

²Department of Pharmacology, Karpagam Faculty of Medical Science and Research,
Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India , 641032.

^{3*}Department of Pharmacology, Karpagam Faculty of Medical Science and Research,
Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India , 641032.

⁴Department of Dravyaguna, Sri Adi Siva Sadguru Alli Saheb Sivaryula Ayurveda Medical
College, Guntakal, Andhra Pradesh, India , 515803.

⁵Department of Dravyaguna, S.V. Ayurvedic Medical College, Tirupathi, Andhra Pradesh,
India, 517507.

^{3*}Corresponding author

Dr Nalinidevi Jayabalan,

Assistant professor,

Department of Pharmacology,

Karpagam Faculty of Medical Science and Research, Coimbatore,

ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND: Osteoarthritis (OA) is the most common degenerative joint disorder that affects one or more diarthrodial joints. Traditional medicinal extracts are used for the treatment of arthritis worldwide. The studies done on *Cissus quadrangularis Linn.* and *Zingiber officinalis Rosc.* also showed anti-inflammatory property. Therefore, this study aimed to describe histopathological changes observed in osteoarthritis induced male wistar rats was treated with *Cissus quadrangularis Linn.* and *Zingiber officinalis Rosc.*

METHODS: There are five groups of male wistar rats were selected, each group consisting of 6 animals. Group I -Control(Normal saline); Group-II- Dexamethasone-8 ml/kg orally; Group III – *Cissus quadrangularis Linn.* - 450 mg/kg; Group IV- *Zingiber officinale Rosc.* - 450 mg/kg; Group V - *Cissus quadrangularis Linn.* with *Zingiber officinale Rosc.* - 450 mg/kg. Before the experimental procedure, all the animals were pre-treated with single intra-articular injection of 1 mg monosodium iodoacetate (MIA) except control group. At the end of the study, on 28th day animals were euthanized and histopathology of the knee joint was evaluated.

RESULTS: Results showed group V (*Cissus quadrangularis Linn.* with *Zingiber officinalis Rosc.*) was more effective in osteoarthritis induced wistar rats compared to the all other groups.

CONCLUSION: The current study on histopathological changes in osteoarthritis induced male wistar rats which was treated with *Cissus quadrangularis Linn.* and *Zingiber officinalis Rosc.* confirms it as an effective treatment option for osteoarthritis.

KEY WORDS: *Cissus quadrangularis Linn.*, *Zingiber officinale Rosc.*, Osteoarthritis, male wistar rat.

INTRODUCTION:

Globally osteoarthritis (OA) is the most common form of arthritis. Knee joint is the most common site of osteoarthritis. Classically OA presents with joint pain and loss of function, however the disease is highly variable clinically[1,2]. OA affects about 3.3 to 3.6% of the population globally. It can cause moderate to severe disability in 43 million people worldwide[3]. India has highest proliferative OA rate and prevalence of knee osteoarthritis is 22-39% in India[4].

OA is classified into primary and secondary based on etiology. Primary OA is due to mechanical stress, immunity and genetics, inflammation, body weight, increasing age, etc. On other hand, secondary OA is due to trauma, iatrogenic injury or congenital dysplasia[5]. Currently OA is managed with lifestyle modification, drugs and surgery. Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDS) are widely used to treat inflammatory reactions and relieve pain, glucocorticoids, hyaluronic acid, chondroitin sulfate and glucosamine are also frequently used. Besides the effectiveness, these drugs have the potential for cardiorenal, gastrointestinal and hepatic side effects, which increase with dose and treatment duration[6,7].

Also these current therapies failed to avert the degeneration of articular cartilage due to multifarious signalling pathway[8]. Nowadays, researcher shows a great interest in those medicinal agents that are derived from plants because the currently available drugs have side effects and highly expensive[9]. *Cissus quadrangularis* Linn. (*Hadjod*) is an indigenous medicinal plant grown in India, Sri Lanka, and Africa. It has been prescribed in ancient Ayurveda texts by *Bhava Prakasha* and *Chakra Dutta* as a general tonic, especially for the fractured patient. It contains high amount of anabolic steroidal substances, calcium and phosphorus. The extracts has been used widely for the early repair of fractures, gout, back pain and irregular menstruation[10]. *Zingiber officinale* Rosc. (ginger) is the member of Zingiberaceae family, which is widely used as spice or medicinal plant in folk and traditional medicines. The extracts are extensively used as analgesic, anti-inflammatory, anticancer, anti-diabetic, hepato-protective, nephro-protective and antioxidant agents[11]. The current study is to evaluate the histopathological changes in osteoarthritis induced male wistar rats treated with *Cissus quadrangularis* Linn. and *Zingiber officinalis* Rosc.

METHODOLOGY: The experimental study was carried out in Department of Dravyaguna, S.V Ayurcedic Medical College, and Tirupathi. The study was started after obtaining the institutional ethical committee approval.

Animal Experimental Groups:

1. Group I - Normal saline (control) orally.
2. Group II – Treatment of Dexamethasone in a dose of 8 ml/kg orally.(Standard)
3. Group III – Treatment of *Cissus quadrangularis Linn.* in a dose of 450 mg/kg orally.
4. Group IV – Treatment of *Zingiber officinale Rosc.* in a dose 450 mg/kg orally.
5. Group V– Treatment of both *Cissus quadrangularis Linn.* with *Zingiber officinale Rosc.* in a dose of 450 mg/kg orally.

Induction of Osteoarthritis

The rats were anesthetized using Ketamine hydrochloride (50 mg/ml for injection) and Xylazine hydrochloride (20mg/ml for injection) at a ratio of 2:1, 1 ml/kg body wt. were injected intramuscularly into the gluteal muscle after knee joints had been shaved and sterilized and placed in the supine position.

Osteoarthritis was induced by giving a single intra-articular injection of 1 mg monosodium iodoacetate (MIA) (crystal powder M = 185.96 g/mol). MIA was dissolved in physiologic saline and administered in a volume of 50 µL using a 30-gauge needle through the intra patellar ligament of the left knee[12]. After the MIA injection a substantial inflammation of synovial joints was observed in this model. The general health of the animals was monitored. No signs of distress were seen.

Intra-articular injection of monosodium iodoacetate (MIA) induces disorganization of the articular cartilage by inhibiting the activity of glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase in chondrocytes, and this result in, disruption of glycolysis and eventual cell death. These chondrocytes have similar histopathology to that of human OA and the MIA induced OA animal model closely mimics both the pain and structural changes associated with the disease.

Treatment was started 14 days after the MIA injection and it was continued for 28 days (1st day of treatment is 15th day of inducing Osteoarthritis). On 28th day animals were sacrificed, than the histopathology of the knee joint is evaluated.

Histopathological analysis:

Histological changes were assessed in all rats that had received 1mg/knee of MIA or saline. Animals were killed by chloroform at the time indicated. Soft tissue was removed from the left (osteoarthritic) legs. The patella was removed from each knee to facilitate thorough fixation of the joint. Tissue samples were prepared for light microscopy using standard procedures. Briefly, samples were preserved in 10% neutral-buffered formalin and subsequently decalcified in 5% formic acid for 72 hour. Samples were dehydrated in an ethanol series and embedded in paraffin. Sections were stained with either hematoxylin–eosin or toluidine blue. Histopathological change of each knee was quantitatively expressed simply by the summation of individual grades [slight: 1(+); moderate: 2(++); severe: 3(+++)] and calculating the average pathology scores, for each finding.

Chondrocyte changes:

Structural change in the joint surface, ulceration, fibrillation of cartilage surface, disorganization of chondrocytes, exposure of subchondral bones, and cellular changes in hypertrophied chondrocytes was studied.

Inflammatory changes:

Degeneration and necrosis in the joint, inflammatory cell infiltration in synovial tissue, synovial cell proliferation, and uptake of Safranin-O staining.

Statistical analysis:

All results are given as mean \pm S.E.M. Statistical comparisons were made using one-way ANOVA and analysed by SPSS software version 21. A value of $p < 0.001$ was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS:

Histopathological changes were observed in Normal, Standard and test drug groups. On 28th day of treatment changes were compared with the knee histopathology of normal rat(normal saline).

TABLE -1: HISTOPATHOLOGICAL FINDINGS

Areas	NS	MIA + DMO	MIA + CQL	MIA + ZOR	MIA + CQL+ ZOR
Chondrocyte damage area	N	+	++	++	+
Chondrocyte Necrosis	N	++	+	++	N
Erosion of Cartilage	N	++	++	+	+
Inflammatory cells in synovial fluid	N	N	N	N	N
Synovial Proliferation	N	N	+	+	N

Score: N= Normal, + = Mild, ++ = Moderate, +++ = Severe

Normal Saline (NS), *Cissus quadrangularis* Linn. (CQL), *Zingiber officinale* Rosc. (ZOR), Dexamethasone (DMO), Monosodium iodoacetate (MIA)

In standard drug group the chondrocyte layer was slightly damaged with no synovial proliferation was observed. Presence of the inflammatory cells was absent. Chondrocyte necrosis and Erosion of Cartilage were moderately observed.

In CQL group chondrocyte layer was moderately damaged with the slight synovial proliferation was observed. Presence of the inflammatory cells was absent. Chondrocyte necrosis was mild and erosion of cartilage was moderately observed.

In ZOR group the chondrocyte layer was moderately damaged with the slight synovial proliferation was observed. Presence of the inflammatory cells was absent. Chondrocyte necrosis was moderate and erosion of cartilage was mildly observed.

In combination of CQL with ZOR group chondrocyte layer was slightly damaged with no synovial proliferation was observed. Presence of the inflammatory cells and erosion of cartilage were mildly observed. Chondrocyte necrosis was absent (Table 1).

FIGURE 1: HISTOPATHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN KNEE JOINT

	<p>Normal control Group</p> <p>Normal tissue</p>
	<p>MIA + DMO</p> <p>Slight Chondrocyte damage. Chondrocyte Necrosis and Erosion of Cartilage moderately observed</p> <p>Absence of inflammatory cells in synovial fluid.</p> <p>No Synovial proliferation.</p>
	<p>MIA + CQL</p> <p>Moderate chondrocyte damage. Slight Chondrocyte necrosis and moderate erosion of cartilage. Absence of inflammatory cells in synovial fluid.</p> <p>Less Synovial proliferation.</p>

	<p>MIA + ZOR</p> <p>Moderate chondrocyte damage.</p> <p>Absence of inflammatory cells in synovial fluid.</p> <p>Moderate chondrocyte necrosis and slight erosion of cartilage</p> <p>Less Synovial proliferation.</p>
	<p>MIA + CQL+ZOR</p> <p>Slight chondrocyte damage.</p> <p>Absence of inflammatory cells in synovial fluid.</p> <p>Normal chondrocyte necrosis and slight erosion of cartilage.</p> <p>Absence of Synovial proliferation.</p>

DISCUSSION:

The present study evaluated histopathological changes in osteoarthritis induced male wistar rat. This study was conducted as per CCSEA guidelines. Totally 30 male wistar rats were grouped into five and all the animals were pre-treated with Intra-articular injection of monosodium iodoacetate (MIA) to induce osteoarthritis except Group I(normal rat).

The previous study done by Hwang et al; demonstrated that effects on *Zingiber officinale* can prevent disease progression of arthritis[13]. Leach et al; done a systematic review which showed that use of *Zingiber officinale* is safe and effective for osteoarthritis patient[14]. Another study by Londhe SB et al; found that, combination therapy of *Cissus quadrangularis* and *Dalbergia sissoo* showed improvement in knee osteoarthritis[15]. Lakshmanan DK et al; done a study on , CQSE (*Cissus quadrangularis* stem) and CQRE (*Cissus quadrangularis* root) extracts in MIA induced osteoarthritis, in which CQSE showed better improvement of arthritis compared to CQRE[16].

There are many studies proved that, *Cissus quadrangularis Linn.* and *Zingiber officinalis Rosc.* on preventing osteoarthritis. The current study was evaluated histopathologically to confirm the anti-inflammatory property in osteoarthritis induced wistar rats which was treated with *Cissus quadrangularis Linn.*, *Zingiber officinalis Rosc.* by sacrificing the rats on 28th day. Result shows that inflammatory cells in synovial fluid came to normal in all the groups. In combination of CQL with ZOR group chondrocyte layer was slightly damaged with no synovial proliferation was observed. Presence of the inflammatory cells and erosion of cartilage were mildly observed in combination group. Current study results proved that, this therapeutic approach is effective in osteoarthritis and can cause alleviation of histopathological dysfunction.

CONCLUSION: Present study revealed that, the combination treatment with *Cissus quadrangularis Linn.* with *Zingiber officinalis Rosc.* was more effective compared to the treatment of *Cissus quadrangularis Linn.* or *Zingiber officinalis Rosc.* alone.

REFERENCES:

1. Bortoluzzi A, Furini F, Scirè CA. Osteoarthritis and its management - Epidemiology, nutritional aspects and environmental factors. *Autoimmun Rev.* 2018 Nov;17(11):1097-1104.
2. Prieto-Alhambra D, Judge A, Javaid MK, Cooper C, Diez-Perez A, Arden NK. Incidence and risk factors for clinically diagnosed knee, hip and hand osteoarthritis: Influences of age, gender and osteoarthritis affecting other joints. *Ann Rheum Dis.* 2014;73:1659–1664.
3. Berenbaum F, Wallace IJ, Lieberman DE, Felson DT. Modern-day environmental factors in the pathogenesis of osteoarthritis. *Nat Rev Rheumatol.* 2018 Nov;14(11):674-681.
4. Das AK, Routray D, Panigrahi TK. Prevalence and risk factors of knee osteoarthritis in a rural community of Odisha: A snap shot study. *JMSCR.* 2018;6:15-21.
5. Felson DT, Lawrence RC, Dieppe PA, Hirsch R, Helmick CG, Jordan JM, Kington RS, Lane NE, Nevitt MC, Zhang Y, et al. Osteoarthritis: New insights. Part 1: The disease and its risk factors. *Ann Intern Med.* 2000;133:635–646.

6. Bindu, S., Mazumder, S., and Bandyopadhyay, U. (2020). Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) and organ damage: A current perspective. *Biochem. Pharmacol.*
7. Chen, D., Su, X., Wang, N., Li, Y., Yin, H., and Li, L., (2017). Chemical isotope labeling LC-MS for monitoring disease progression and treatment in animal models: Plasma metabolomics study of osteoarthritis rat model. *Sci. Rep.*
8. Shah FH, kim SJ. Therapeutic role of medicinal plant extracts and bioactive compounds in osteoarthritis. *Journal of cardiovascular translational research.*2022;22:837-844
9. Badami S, Moorkoth S, Suresh B. *Caesalpinia sappan* a medicinal and dye yielding plant. *Nat Prod Rad* 2004;3:75-82.
10. Brahmshatriva HR, Shah KA, Ananthkumar GB, Brahmshatriva MH. Clinical evaluation of *Cissus quadrangularis* as osteogenic agent in maxillofacial ; A pilot study. *Ayu.* 2015 ; 36(2): 169–173
11. Mahboubi M. *Zingiber officinale* rosc. Essential oil, a review on its composition and bioactivity. *Clinical Phytoscience.* 2019;5
12. Takahashi I, Matsuzaki T, Kuroki H, Hosono M. Induction of osteoarthritis by injecting monosodium iodoacetate into the patellofemoral joint of an experimental rat model. *PLoS One.* 2018;13(4)
13. Hwang JH, Jung HW, Oh SY, Kang JS, Kim JP, Park YK. Effects of *Zingiber officinale* extract on collagen -induced arthritis in mice and IL- 1 β -induced inflammation in human synovial fibroblasts. *European journal of inflammation.* 2017
14. Leach, J M, Kumar, Saravana. The clinical effectiveness of Ginger (*Zingiber Officinale*) in adults with osteoarthritis. *JBIC Library of systematic reviews.* 6(8):310-323
15. Londhe SB, Shah RV, Desouza C, Londhe V, Singh D. Early experience with the use of *Cissus quadrangularis* and *Dalbergia sissoo* therapy on bone marrow edema and knee pain associated with degenerative medial compartment knee osteoarthritis. *Asian journal of medical science.*2024;15(4)
16. Lakshmanan DK, Ravichandran G, Elangovan A, Jeyapaul P, Murugesan S, Thilagar S. *Cissus quadrangularis* (velvet grape) attenuates disease progression and anatomical changes in mono sodium iodoacetate (MIA)-induced knee osteoarthritis in the rat model. *Food and function.*2020